

URBAN CHALLENGES AND SPATIAL TRANSFORMATION IN MANGHOPIR, KARACHI

A CASE STUDY ON INFRASTRUCTURE, LAND USE, AND SOCIO- ENVIRONMENTAL CONDITIONS

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15862158>

Keywords

Manghopir, peri-urban development, informal urbanization, infrastructure, Global South

Article History

Received: 23 September 2024
Accepted: 23 December 2024
Published: 30 December 2024

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Abstract

This research investigates the physical and built environment of Manghopir, an old and evolving neighborhood in Karachi, Pakistan. The study focuses on spatial dynamics, infrastructural conditions, and socio-environmental challenges emerging from rapid, unplanned urbanization. Manghopir, historically known for its cultural significance and religious heritage, is now increasingly shaped by commercial expansion, informal settlements, and industrial activity, particularly marble processing. The study divides the 965-acre area into four distinct zones and analyzes their respective development patterns, road networks, building morphology, vegetation, and utility infrastructure. A mixed-methods approach was adopted, comprising field surveys, direct observations, structured interviews, photographic documentation, and mapping. Key findings reveal severe issues, such as deteriorating roads, inadequate drainage, insufficient green spaces, random encroachments, and hazardous electric lines. The lack of cohesive urban planning, combined with weak governance and overlapping institutional roles, has amplified the environmental degradation and poor quality of life for residents. This paper argues that with a targeted planning framework and stakeholder collaboration, the deteriorating conditions in Manghopir can be systematically improved. The findings aim to inform sustainable urban design, public infrastructure development, and future policy planning in peri-urban and marginalized areas of Karachi, offering replicable lessons for other rapidly urbanizing regions in the Global South.

INTRODUCTION

Urbanization in developing cities often follows uneven, unregulated patterns, leading to a range of infrastructural, social, and environmental challenges. Karachi, which is the largest metropolis in Pakistan, epitomizes this trajectory (Hasan, 2021; Hasan, et.al;2013). Over recent decades, the city has experienced rapid economic growth, resulting in the proliferation of new settlements. However, this

expansion has often come at the expense of older neighbourhoods that hold significant historical and cultural value, which remain neglected (Hasan, et.al; 2013). Critically, this urban growth has proceeded in the absence of coherent and enforceable planning frameworks, particularly in peripheral and historically marginalized areas such as Manghopir (Anwar, et.al; 2021).

Manghopir is situated in Gadap town, on the northwestern fringe of Karachi, Pakistan, and positioned in the hilly terrain between the districts of Karachi, Sindh, and Lasbela, Baluchistan. The area holds significant religious and historical importance, being home to one of the oldest Sufi shrines in the region. Commonly known as Manghopir, the shrine is attributed to Khawaja Sakhi Hassan Sultan Mangho, a revered Sufi saint, whose resting place draws pilgrims from Pakistan and abroad. Over the past two decades, the area has undergone rapid spatial and demographic transformation and presents a dynamic case of urban evolution from being a religious-cultural hub to a dense residential zone and an industrial hub (Sheikh, 2023; Roth et. al, 2019). One of the most dominant drivers of this transformation has been the unconstrained expansion of the marble industry, especially along the Manghopir Road. These activities, particularly those related to marble processing, contribute to significant air and noise pollution (Roth et. al, 2019). Without sufficient tree cover or buffer zones, these pollutants directly impact residential zones, exposing residents to respiratory and psychological health risks (Sheng, 2018). Moreover, the emergence of large-scale real estate projects in proximity, such as Naya Nazimabad, has exacerbated further pressure on Manghopir's already overburdened infrastructure and limited public resources (Gayer, 2015). Moreover, in Manghopir, narrow tertiary roads, overcrowded residential clusters, haphazard building morphology, and scarcity of open spaces reflect a broader urban condition shaped by informality, economic constraints, and weak regulatory frameworks.

Despite its socio-cultural importance, Manghopir remains largely neglected in formal city planning documents, due to overlapping jurisdictions, regulatory challenges, and resource constraints. Therefore, this research aims to analyze and document the current conditions of Manghopir's built and physical environment, with a focus on four defined zones: (1) Pakhtoonabad and the Manghopir shrine precinct, (2) the industrial marble zone and Abdul Rehman Goth, (3) Mianwali Colony and adjacent neighborhoods, and (4) Islamia Colony I & II. These zones were selected for their unique functional typologies, transportation networks,

demographic characteristics, and infrastructural disparities.

By synthesizing empirical data from fieldwork, community feedback, and mapping analysis with broader urban theory, this study contributes to the growing body of literature on urban inequality, informal urbanism, and sustainable development in South Asian cities (Hasan et. al, 2015). It underscores the urgent need for inclusive and context-specific planning approaches in Karachi's peripheries, approaches that engage communities, recognize socio-spatial diversity, and build institutional capacity.

1. The study area: Manghopir

1.1. Contextual background

Manghopir is called a rural area in the neighbourhoods of Gadap town, named after a famous Sufi saint "Pir Haji Syed Sakhi Sultan" or "Pir Mangho" as "Manghopir". The existence of Manghopir dates to the 12th century. The first attraction of the region is the mazaar of Sufi saint Pir Mangho, which lies on these premises. It is one of the oldest Sufi shrines present in the city. Based on archeological research, the area where Manghopir Mazar lives today had been religiously significant in the Bronze Age as well, where people worshiped crocodiles (Sheng, 2018). This is also a major reason that people of different beliefs and cultures are attracted to this zone. However, recent decades have witnessed a shift in the area's urban identity from a spiritual retreat to a contested and industrialized urban margin. This transformation is consistent with broader urban trends in Karachi, where heritage-rich neighborhoods are being encroached upon or reconfigured under the pressure of speculative real estate development and industrial growth (Gayer, 2015). The emergence of the marble industry along Manghopir Road has been a key catalyst in the area's spatial and ecological transformation. These activities, largely unregulated, have contributed to severe environmental degradation, including dust pollution, noise, and solid waste accumulation conditions that are exacerbated by a lack of green buffers and proper zoning (Anwar, et.al; 2021). Once an area of socio-cultural significance, the entire Manghopir, today, houses commercial activities. which is about 965 acres, is mainly a commercial hub for many marble factories and informal transactions. It accommodates

residents belonging to diverse regional backgrounds, cultures, and religions. The main areas that fall under Manghopir are Pakhtoonabad, Abdul Rehman Goth, the industrial zone (where marble factories are built adjacent to each other), Mianwali and New Mianwali Colony, Kunwari Colony, Iqbal Nagar, Islamia Colony I and II along with a prominent Shrine of the great Sufi Pir Haji Syed Sakhi Sultan Mangho.

1.2. Manghopir and Its Urban Zones

Owing to the vast linear stretch of the study area, it has been divided into four discrete zones, encompassing differences in land use, population density, physical infrastructure, and economic activity, as shown in Figure 1. The divisions will benefit in steering a focused and comparative analysis across the site.

Figure 1: The case study area of Manghopir is divided into four urban zones

a. Zone 1: Pakhtoonabad and the Manghopir shrine precinct

This zone spans approximately 340 acres and represents the cultural and religious heart of Manghopir. It houses the Manghopir Shrine, the crocodile pond, and the Dadex Eternit Limited Factory, along with a large cemetery and dense residential clusters, such as Pakhtoonabad. The built form is informal and organic, with narrow internal roads and irregular plot sizes. The primary road, which connects the shrine area to Naya Nazimabad and other parts of Karachi, is congested and lacks pedestrian infrastructure. Informal vendors line the roadside, often encroaching onto the carriageway. Major landmarks include:

- Shrine of Manghopir

- Al Badar Medical Center
- K-electric Grid Station
- Govenment Boys and Girls Primary School
- Khanjee General Hospital

Despite its religious significance, the area suffers from poor waste management, air and noise pollution from adjacent industrial zones, and minimal green cover.

b. Zone 2: The industrial marble zone and Abdul Rehman Goth

Covering about 120 acres, Zone 2 is the principal industrial zone, dominated by marble factories and warehouses. This sector includes Abdul Rehman Goth, a small residential enclave adjacent to the industrial strip. The factories produce significant particulate matter and dust, contributing to poor air

quality and deteriorating public health. Due to high levels of truck traffic, this zone experiences frequent road congestion and random parking of heavy vehicles. Street widths are irregular, and the lack of designated parking and loading areas exacerbates the circulation problems.

Major landmarks include:

- Millat Marble Factory
- Shah Khalid Autos
- PSO Petrol Pump

c. Zone 3: Mianwali Colony and adjacent neighborhoods

This 275-acre residential zone is home to ethnically diverse groups, including migrants from Mianwali, Hazara, and Gilgit-Baltistan. The urban fabric is a patchwork of self-constructed houses, often built incrementally without adherence to planning norms or building codes. Streets are narrow and winding, limiting vehicular access and emergency response. The presence of community-level institutions like mosques and schools gives the area a semi-formal identity. However, open spaces are rare, and encroachments are common. The shortage of green space and poor ventilation contribute to heat stress, especially during summer months.

Major landmarks include:

- Rehan Hospital
- Al Sufa Mosque
- Hill Town Public Elementary School
- Markhor Rock Salt Lamps Shop

Zone 4: Islamia Colony I & II

Spanning approximately 230 acres, Zone 4 comprises Islamia Colony I and II, predominantly inhabited by Pashtun families. The area has a visibly higher population density, and the spatial arrangement is congested, with limited open spaces and overlapping residential and commercial land uses. Unlike other zones, this area has a relatively active Union Council (UC 9), which acts as a semi-functional governance node. However, basic infrastructure remains underdeveloped. The spatial condition of this zone reflects broader patterns of neglect in Karachi’s informal settlements, where population growth has outpaced infrastructural development.

Major landmarks include:

- H.B. Marble Industry
- Ghausia Boys and Girls Schools
- Tayyaba Mosque
- Mustafa Jamia Mosque

Table 1: Summary of Zonal Characteristics- Zone 1, Zone 2, Zone 3, and Zone 4

Zones	Primary function	Area (acres)	Dominant features
Zone 1	Religious/Cultural/Residential	340	Manghopir Shrine, Pakhtoonabad, informal housing, low tree cover
Zone 2	Industrial	120	Marble factories, truck traffic, air pollution, lack of basic civic infrastructure
Zone 3	High and low-density Residential	275	Self-constructed incrementally built houses, schools, sewerage overflow, intermittent electricity supply, poor road access, diverse ethnic population
Zone 4	High-density Residential	230	Informal waste disposal system, irregular water supply, kunda system, dense population

This division allows a focused understanding of Manghopir’s unique but interconnected urban challenges. In the sections that follow, the paper

analyzes these zones in greater depth through thematic lenses such as transportation, infrastructure, vegetation, and land use.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

To comprehensively understand the evolving physical and social conditions of Manghopir, this study employs a qualitative research design. Given the complexity of the urban challenges under investigation, ranging from infrastructure gaps and environmental degradation to socio-economic inequality, this approach ensures a more nuanced and grounded analysis.

The study draws upon both primary and secondary data sources:

- **Primary data** was obtained through fieldwork, including surveys, interviews, direct observations, site documentation (photographs and sketches), and mapping.
- **Secondary data** includes government records, planning documents (e.g., KSDP-2020, SBCA regulations), reports from local NGOs, media reports, and academic literature on urban development in Karachi.

2.1. Data Collection Tools

2.1.1. Field Surveys and Observations

Extensive field visits were conducted across all four zones of Manghopir. These visits enabled the research team to assess the condition of roads, drainage systems, pedestrian infrastructure, building types, vegetation, and public spaces. The surveys included:

- Mapping road hierarchies (primary, secondary, and tertiary roads)
- Visual assessments of infrastructure conditions (e.g., street lighting, drainage, sewerage)
- Photographic documentation of congestion points, encroachments, and vegetation

2.1.2. Interviews and Focus Group Discussions

A combination of **structured and unstructured interviews** was conducted with key stakeholders:

- Residents, including both long-term dwellers and recent migrants
- Local shopkeepers and industrial workers, particularly in Zones 1 and 2
- Community leaders and school administrators, especially in Zones 3 and 4

- Union Council representatives from UC 9 (Islamia Colony)
 - Factory owners and operators in the marble sector
- These discussions provided critical insights into residents lived experiences, their perceptions of development, and coping strategies for infrastructural deficits.

2.1.3. Questionnaire Survey

A standardized questionnaire was distributed among 80 households across the four zones, targeting a representative sample of age, gender, and income groups. Questions focused on:

- Access to utilities (water, electricity, gas)
- Quality of roads and pedestrian safety
- Frequency and type of environmental hazards
- Satisfaction with green/open spaces
- Willingness to participate in community-led interventions

Demographic data such as household size, income range (PKR 20,000–50,000/month), employment type, and education level were also collected to contextualize responses.

2.1.4. Mapping and Geospatial Analysis

Basic GIS tools were used to:

- Create land use maps distinguishing residential, commercial, and industrial zones
 - Analyze traffic congestion points and access corridors
 - Identify voids and green cover across the study area
- Although high-resolution satellite imagery was limited, field-verified sketch maps provided a reliable spatial framework.

2.2. Data Analysis Tools

2.2.1. Thematic Analysis

Applied to interview transcripts, focus group notes, and field observations that help identify recurring themes such as perceptions of neglect, environmental concerns, informal coping strategies, and community resilience.

2.2.2. Content Analysis

For systematically analyzing qualitative responses in the open-ended sections of surveys and interviews. Useful for comparing narratives across zones (e.g.,

different priorities between residents of Zones 1 and 4).

2.2.3. Photographic and Sketch Interpretation

Visual data from field documentation was analyzed using visual coding frameworks (e.g., types of infrastructure, land encroachments, vegetation conditions).

3. FINDINGS AND ANALYSIS

The findings revealed challenges related to transportation, vegetation, infrastructure, and land use.

The main Manghopir Road across the four zones is 4.5 km long and 160 feet wide, and it starts from Qalandariya Chowk to Mango Peer Mazar as shown in Figure 2. Mostly, movement of traffic includes heavy traffic, public and private vehicles, motorbikes, and cycles, as shown in Figures 3a and 3b. Transportation in Manghopir is characterized by severe congestion, unregulated vehicular movement, lack of pedestrian infrastructure, and randomized spatial planning. These issues are prevalent across all four zones, though their intensity and manifestations vary depending on land use, population density, and industrial activity.

3.1. Transportation and Road Networks

Figure 2: Manghopir main Arterial Road map across the four zones

3.1.1. Road Hierarchy and Conditions

Despite its width, the main Manghopir Road corridor fails to support smooth vehicular flow due to poor maintenance, irregular surface treatment, encroachments, and unplanned intersections, as shown in Figures 3a and 3b. The road is flanked by informal markets, encroaching vendor stalls, and randomly parked vehicles, especially trucks servicing marble factories in Zone 2. Secondary roads, typically

35 feet wide, traverse the internal neighborhoods of Pakhtoonabad, Mianwali Colony, and Islamia Colony as shown in Figures 4a and 4b. These roads lack signage, are poorly paved, and often intersect at irregular angles, leading to traffic bottlenecks and safety risks. Tertiary lanes, ranging between 12 to 20 feet in width, dominate the inner fabric of residential areas and are inaccessible to emergency or waste collection vehicles, as shown in Figures 5a and 5b.

Figures 3a and 3b: Primary Street views of Manghopir Road

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Figures 4a and 4b: Secondary Street views of Manghopir Road

A major finding from field observation and community interviews is that road infrastructure in Manghopir does not match the functional intensity of the area. Zones designated for industrial activity have no designated loading bays, turning radii for heavy vehicles, or buffer zones to separate pedestrian movement from truck circulation.

3.1.2. Traffic Patterns and Congestion Points

The traffic in Manghopir includes a mix of heavy trucks, public minibuses (F-11, F-22, W-22), rickshaws, Qingqis, bicycles, and pedestrian traffic. This multi-modal mix operates on roads without lane markings or regulatory signage, resulting in chaotic circulation. Specific congestion hotspots identified during fieldwork include:

- The intersection of the main road and Pakhtoonabad’s secondary entry (Zone 1)
- Millat Marble Factory junction in the industrial sector (Zone 2)
- Roadside commercial strips in Islamia Colony (Zone 4)
- Points near schools and mosques, where vehicular and pedestrian flows overlap

Due to the absence of controlled access points, vehicles frequently enter from non-standard angles, causing conflict points and increasing the risk of accidents. No formal bus stops or pedestrian crossings exist along the entire 4.5 km stretch of the primary road, compelling commuters to cross through moving traffic.

Figure 6: Congestion points across the four zones

3.1.3. Encroachments and Informal Activities

A common theme across all zones is the encroachment of pedestrian walkways and service lanes by vendors, mechanic workshops, and temporary stalls. Near the Manghopir Shrine, vendors selling food, amulets, and religious goods have permanently occupied sections of the road. These encroachments reduce the effective width of the carriageway and add to visual and physical clutter. In

Zone 2, marble-cutting activities spill over onto road margins, creating piles of debris and dust as shown in Figure 8. These encroachments block drainage lines, damage the asphalt, and cause health hazards due to marble dust inhalation. Interviews with truck drivers and factory owners revealed that there is no designated parking or loading/unloading zone, which forces them to halt on the road.

Figure 8: Spillover of marble factories in Zone 2

3.1.4. Pedestrian and Non-Motorized Transport (NMT)

The absence of pedestrian infrastructure, such as sidewalks, raised crossings, and buffers, is one of the most critical gaps. Residents, including children and elderly people, must walk directly on the main road or squeeze through vendor-dense secondary lanes, exposing themselves to constant vehicular risk. Only 18% of the households surveyed said they feel safe walking in the area. Cyclists, mainly laborers and schoolchildren, also lack dedicated tracks. Field observation noted that bicycles are forced to share lanes with trucks and motorbikes, a dangerous situation amplified during peak traffic hours.

3.1.5. Drainage and Road Safety Hazards

Many roads, especially in Zones 3 and 4, have open drains running parallel to carriageways. These open stormwater and sewage channels are often uncovered, emitting foul odors and posing tripping hazards, as shown in Figures 9a and 9b. During the monsoon season, rainwater stagnates in potholes and broken pavement sections, worsening congestion and increasing the risk of accidents. Notably, street lighting is inconsistent, with major segments in Zones 2 and 4 remaining unlit at night, contributing to security concerns.

Figure 9a and 9b: Road safety hazards on Manghopir Road

3.1.6. Public Transport Access

Public transportation is minimal and irregular in Manghopir. The available buses and Qingqis do not follow fixed schedules, and there are no marked pick-up or drop-off zones. Most residents rely on walking

or sharing rickshaws to reach transit nodes outside the area. Survey responses indicate that 63% of residents travel over 1 km to access reliable public transport, while 76% report feeling unsafe during their

commute, particularly during evening hours, due to poor lighting and lack of footpaths.

3.1.7. Key Challenges Identified

Table 2 below identifies and summarizes transportation challenges in Manghopir, and Chart 1 below, statistically analyzes mobility data according to field-based surveys.

3.2. Vegetation and Environmental Analysis

Vegetation and environmental quality in Manghopir are significantly compromised due to dense

unplanned construction, industrial pollution, and limited green infrastructure. The absence of structured landscaping and environmental buffers not only affects microclimatic comfort but also contributes to public health deterioration and psychological stress among residents. Across all four zones of the study area, vegetation was found to be scarce, unevenly distributed, and poorly maintained, as shown in Figure 10.

Table 2: Transportation challenges and their description

Challenge	Description
Poor road surface conditions	Cracks, potholes, waterlogging, and lack of asphalt resurfacing
Lack of pedestrian infrastructure	Absence of sidewalks, crossings, and footbridges
Unregulated parking and loading	Trucks and stalls are blocking traffic flow
Absence of signage and street furniture	No road signs, seating, or wayfinding
Inadequate lighting	Especially in residential and industrial backstreets
Unsafe cycling conditions	No bike lanes; forced sharing with heavy vehicles
Encroached roadsides	Informal vendors and debris from marble factories

Chart 1: Field-based Statistics of transportation mobility challenges in Manghopir

Figure 10: Landscape distribution in Manghopir

3.2.1. Existing Vegetation Profile

Field observations and mapping revealed that vegetation in Manghopir is sporadic and primarily consists of a few tree species scattered along road margins and within mosque or school courtyards. The most observed species, as shown in Figures 11a-11d, included:

- **Khajur (Date Palm)** – slow-growing, limited shade
- **Conocarpus** – fast-growing, tall, but ecologically controversial
- **Maharukh** – native species with rapid growth
- **Sufeda (Eucalyptus)** – common but with high water absorption and low ecological value

Figure 11a: Khajur Tree

Figure 11b: Conocarpus

Figure 11c: Maharukh

Figure 11d: Sufeda

Figure 12a: Lack of tree cover

Figure 12b: Barren open plots

These trees are predominantly found along the main Manghopir Road and near some schools and religious sites. However, their coverage is insufficient to regulate ambient temperature or filter industrial pollutants, especially in Zones 2 and 3, where

3.2.2. Zone-wise Environmental Conditions

- **Zone 1:** Despite being a cultural hub, Zone 1 lacks public green spaces or shaded areas. Pilgrims and vendors operate in exposed environments. Limited tree cover near the shrine does not extend to the surrounding residential areas. Dust levels remain high due to nearby roads and informal markets.
- **Zone 2:** This zone exhibits extreme environmental stress. Marble cutting generates large quantities of airborne particulates. No vegetation buffers exist between factories and residential pockets. Interviews revealed high incidences of respiratory illness and dust allergies among workers and nearby residents.
- **Zone 3:** A few schools have trees within their compounds, but the rest of the area is heavily built up. The absence of shade during hot months contributes to heat stress, especially for school children and daily laborers, amplified by concrete surfaces and a lack of ventilation.
- **Zone 4:** Vegetation here is nearly absent. Empty spaces are occupied by construction waste, abandoned presents field-based statistical data of the same.

industrial and residential uses collide. The backstreets and internal tertiary lanes of all zones lack any meaningful vegetation, as shown in Figure 12a-12b. Open plots, if any, are usually barren, used for garbage dumping, or encroached upon by informal structures.

vehicles, or unauthorized parking. Residents expressed frustration over the lack of parks or shaded pathways.

• 3.2.3. Public Space and Park Conditions

While official land use maps indicate the presence of public parks in Zones 3 and 4, site visits revealed that these parks are non-functional. Most were barren, lacked grass or vegetation, and were either locked, abandoned, or used for illicit activities after dark. In focus group discussions, residents emphasized the need for recreational green space but noted that existing plots are either claimed by influential actors or encroached upon by vendors or settlers.

3.2.4. Environmental Challenges

Table 3 below presents some major environmental challenges and their impacts in Manghopir and Chart 3 below

Table 3: Environmental challenges and impacts in Manghopir

Challenge	Impact
Sparse vegetation	Urban heat, lack of shade, and low comfort
Industrial dust	Respiratory illness, poor air quality
No functional parks	Physical inactivity, mental stress
Lack of green buffers	Noise and pollution intrusion
Unused land not greened	Garbage dumping, encroachments

Chart 2: Field-based statistics on Environmental Challenges and their impact on Manghopir

In conclusion, the vegetation and environmental conditions in Manghopir are severely inadequate and require urgent greening interventions to restore ecological balance and support public health. Integrating low-cost, community-driven green infrastructure can significantly improve livability, especially in a climate-vulnerable megacity like Karachi.

3.3. Infrastructure and Utilities: Electricity, Water, Sewerage, and Gas

Infrastructure in Manghopir is highly uneven, reflecting a broader pattern of exclusion and neglect commonly found in peripheral settlements of megacities. Although some services like electricity and gas are present in parts of the area, many basic utilities

remain poorly developed, irregular, or absent in several zones. Field surveys and interviews revealed critical gaps in sewerage, water supply, and drainage systems, posing threats to public health and environmental safety.

3.3.1. Electricity Supply and Distribution

Electricity in Manghopir is primarily provided by K-Electric, Karachi’s sole power distribution utility. While the main road and marble factories are relatively well-connected, there are many interior residential streets, especially in Zones 3 and 4, that face frequent load shedding, low voltage, and safety hazards, as shown in Figures 13a-13b.

Electricity poles are present across all zones, but several issues persist:

- Use of kunda (illegal connections) remains widespread, especially in Zones 3 and 4, leading to power theft and overloading of the grid.
- High-tension wires pass dangerously close to residential units and schools in Zones 2 and 4, risking electrocution and fire.

- Factories in Zone 2 have individual transformers (PMTs) rated at 150–250 kV, supplying their electricity networks, often without regulatory oversight.
- Several streetlights are either broken or non-functional, resulting in poorly lit roads that compromise public safety at night.

Figures 13a and 13b: Situation of Electricity Transmission in Manghopir

Respondents stated that outages were not only inconvenient but dangerous, as they disable water pumps, disrupt school operations, and increase theft risk in darker streets.

serious contamination and health risks. No systematic monitoring or maintenance schedule from KWSB was reported by residents.

3.3.2. Water Supply and Distribution

Water provision in Manghopir falls under the jurisdiction of the Karachi Water and Sewerage Board (KWSB). However, in practice, the water supply system is fragmented and highly unreliable. Zones 1 and 2, being closer to the main road, have relatively better access to piped water, while internal residential colonies in Zones 3 and 4 face chronic shortages.

Findings from field surveys include:

- Water is delivered through a mix of formal pipelines, informal connections, and water tankers.
- In many backstreets, the water lines are ruptured or leak into adjacent sewerage drains, contaminating the supply and reducing pressure.
- Electric motors are widely used by households to pump water, particularly in higher elevation areas.
- Several households reported paying between PKR 1,200–2,000 per month for privately supplied water tankers, especially during summer shortages. A major problem is the overlap of drinking water and greywater lines, particularly in Zone 3, which creates

3.3.3. Sewerage and Drainage System

The sewerage infrastructure is perhaps the most degraded utility in Manghopir, as shown in Figures 14a-14b. Only parts of Zone 1 and Zone 2 have semi-functional underground lines. The remaining areas rely on open drains, which are often clogged, broken, or misaligned with the natural topography.

Critical observations include:

- Open sewerage lines pass through residential alleys in Zones 3 and 4, many of which are uncovered and overflow during rain.
- Blockages are common, especially where debris from marble factories or household garbage is dumped.
- Several manholes are either broken or missing covers, creating serious safety hazards, especially for children.
- The topography of the area, with slopes and depressions, causes natural pooling of wastewater in low-lying zones during monsoon, worsening sanitation.

Figure 14a: Dumping in sewage lines

Figure 14b: Open sewage drains

Residents reported frequent cases of waterborne diseases, including skin infections, diarrhea, and eye irritations. The mixing of sewer and drinking water lines was cited as a key concern.

3.3.4. Gas Supply

Sui Southern Gas Company (SSGC) provides piped gas connections in Manghopir, though, like other services, distribution is uneven.

- In Zone 1 and some parts of Zone 2, houses have registered gas meters and a consistent supply.
- In Zones 3 and 4, many houses use shared lines, flexible rubber pipes, or LPG cylinders, which are less safe and more expensive.

Several households reported using wood or coal stoves during winters due to poor gas pressure or total absence of supply. The marble factories are also connected to the gas grid, but often overuse their quota or divert supply, further straining residential access.

Overall, gas infrastructure is present but poorly regulated, with no clear separation between industrial and residential pipelines.

3.3.5. Telecommunication and Digital Access

Telecommunication infrastructure is developing, but is still limited:

- Mobile phone signals are available but inconsistent inside buildings, especially in Zones 3 and 4.
- Fiber-optic internet is largely absent. Most households rely on mobile data, which is costly and unreliable for school or remote work needs.
- There is no public Wi-Fi or government-supported digital inclusion program in place.

3.3.6 Infrastructure Challenges

Table 4 below summarizes the infrastructure challenges in utility consumption related to electricity, water, sewage, gas, and telecom, and Chart 3 presents field-based statistics of the same.

Table 4: Infrastructure Challenges with identified issues

Utility	Coverage	Issues Identified
Electricity	Moderate	Kunda system, outages, unsafe poles, weak lighting
Water	Low-Moderate	Leakages, contamination, and reliance on tankers
Sewerage	Poor	Open drains, blockages, and health hazards
Gas	Moderate	Irregular supply, informal pipes, safety risks
Telecom	Weak	Poor signal, no fiber, low internet penetration

Chart 3: Field-based statistics on Utility coverage levels and identified issues in Manghopir

These statistics underscore the pressing need for comprehensive infrastructure upgrades, informed by a coordinated urban planning framework and active local stakeholder engagement.

3.4. Building Morphology, Land Use, and Solid-Void Patterns

Manghopir exhibits a highly irregular and organic built environment as shown in Figure 15, reflecting a

combination of informal urban growth, lack of zoning enforcement, and socio-economic constraints. Building morphology, land use patterns, and spatial configurations vary considerably across the four zones but share common characteristics such as low-rise construction, mixed land uses, and poor open space distribution. These physical conditions have direct implications for ventilation, mobility, privacy, environmental health, and future densification.

Figure 15: Area Division Plan across the four zones

3.4.1. Building Typologies and Heights

Across all four zones, the predominant building type is low-rise residential, typically ground + 1 or ground + 2 floors, constructed incrementally with a mix of

concrete, cement blocks, and reused materials. Common typologies include:

- Courtyard houses (chowk-based) in Zone 1 (Pakhtoonabad)

- Row houses and semi-attached units in Zones 3 and 4

- Hybrid residential-commercial buildings in Zones 2 and 4, where shops operate on the ground floor and families reside above

Many buildings have incomplete upper stories, indicating incremental growth based on affordability and family needs. Flat roofs are often used for drying clothes, storing goods, or as additional sleeping space in summer.

Plot sizes vary widely:

- **Zone 1 & 4:** 60–120 sq. yards (compact)
- **Zone 2:** 200+ sq. yards (industrial plots and larger lots)
- **Zone 3:** Mix of 80–150 sq. yards

These small, subdivided plots contribute to high **built density** and insufficient voids between buildings.

3.4.2. Land Use Patterns

Land use in Manghopir is **highly mixed and unregulated**, with residential, commercial, religious, educational, and industrial functions coexisting within short distances. There is no clear zoning distinction, leading to:

- Industrial-residential adjacency in Zone 2 (marble factories next to homes)
- Street-level commercial strips on major roads and at intersections in Zones 1 and 4
- Religious and educational land uses are interspersed within residential areas across all zones
- Absence of clearly designated institutional or recreational zones

This unplanned mixed use creates problems related to noise pollution, dust intrusion, traffic congestion, and poor service delivery. Field mapping shows that **over 65%** of the land in Zones 1, 3, and 4 is used for residential purposes, with the rest divided between commercial (15%), industrial (10%), institutional (5%), and vacant or open plots (5%).

3.4.3. Solid-Void Ratio and Street Widths

The solid-to-void ratio in most residential parts of Manghopir is critically skewed, where solid indicates the built-up area and void represents the open spaces, as shown in Figure 16. Observations indicate that built structures occupy up to 85–90% of the plot area, leaving narrow rear or front setbacks. Voids (open areas) are rare and often serve dual functions: garbage dumping grounds, animal pens, or informal parking.

Figure 16: Solid-void ratio in Manghopir

Street widths are inconsistent and reflect unplanned growth:

- **Tertiary streets:** 12–16 feet wide, often encroached or blocked by household extensions

- **Secondary roads:** 24–36 feet, though reduced by vendor encroachments or debris
- **Primary road:** 160 feet, but effectively narrowed due to lack of enforcement and poor surface condition

3.4.4. Construction Quality and Materials

Construction is largely self-financed and incremental, often without professional architects, structural engineers, or compliance with building codes. Common issues include:

- Irregular plot orientations and alignments
- Use of substandard construction materials (e.g., salvaged bricks, recycled wood)
- Lack of foundations and seismic design, posing collapse risks in earthquakes
- Unsafe staircases, open rooftops, and exposed electrical wiring

Many homes feature makeshift rooftop water tanks and solar panels, indicating resilience strategies but also the lack of central service provision.

3.4.5. Encroachments and Vertical Expansion

Residents, particularly in Zones 3 and 4, frequently encroach upon streets by extending balconies, staircases, or kiosks. This form of horizontal encroachment narrows public paths and creates social friction. Simultaneously, vertical expansion, adding additional floors without structural reinforcement, is becoming more common.

3.4.6. Key Morphological Challenges

Table 5 below presents some notable morphological challenges and implications in Manghopir, and Chart 4 presents field-based statistical data of the same.

Table 5: Morphological challenges and implications across the four zones in Manghopir

Challenge	Implication
High built density	Poor ventilation, heat buildup, and lack of light
Mixed land use	Environmental conflicts, loss of residential quality
Minimal setbacks	Lack of privacy, risk in emergencies
Vertical growth without structural planning	Safety hazards
Encroached lanes	Reduced access and walkability
Lack of zoning	Inefficient service delivery, inconsistent development

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Chart 4: Field-based Statistics of Morphological Challenges and their implications in Manghopir

This analysis of built form and land use patterns reveals how informal growth, while adaptive,

undermines urban sustainability, safety, and equity in Manghopir.

4. Discussion

The findings from Manghopir's four zones present a vivid portrait of spatial inequity, infrastructural neglect, and ad hoc urbanization. These conditions are not isolated; rather, they reflect a broader pattern of marginalization found in Karachi's peripheral neighborhoods, where state institutions retreat and informality fills the void.

i. One of the most consistent themes emerging from the analysis is institutional fragmentation. The lack of coordinated planning authority, combined with overlapping jurisdictions between SBCA, KDA, KMC, and Union Councils, fails to enforce zoning laws, building codes, and service delivery standards. Despite the area's inclusion in past strategic frameworks like KSDP-2020, there is little evidence of implementation or monitoring on the ground. Residents in all zones reported uncertainty about which agency to approach for issues like sewage, road repair, or encroachments. This vacuum has created space for unregulated development, with marble industries operating beside homes, unplanned vertical construction risking collapse, and public land being encroached by private actors.

ii. Manghopir's built morphology and solid-void ratios reveal a city in conflict with its spatial logic. Narrow tertiary streets, inadequate setbacks, and high ground coverage contribute to a lack of ventilation, privacy, and safety. The absence of open and green spaces, especially in Zones 3 and 4, creates microclimatic stress and limits social interaction. Children have no designated play areas, and women often remain confined indoors due to security concerns and lack of accessible, well-maintained public spaces. The environmental stressors are most acute in Zone 2, where marble factory operations result in constant air pollution, dust accumulation, and noise. Yet, no environmental mitigation measures (green buffers, dust filters, zoning buffers) have been implemented. The situation is exacerbated by the absence of vegetation across all zones, contributing to elevated surface temperatures, reduced air quality, and poor mental health outcomes, particularly among vulnerable populations such as children and the elderly.

iii. The study confirms that Manghopir suffers from deep infrastructural inequity. Although services like electricity and gas are present, they are unevenly distributed and poorly regulated. The widespread use of illegal kunda connections, flexible gas piping, and leaking water lines illustrates how residents have created informal solutions in the absence of state provision. While these adaptations ensure survival, they often come with serious safety, health, and financial risks.

iv. Sewerage and drainage systems are in especially critical condition. Open drains, overflowing manholes, and blocked sewage lines were reported in all zones. These issues lead to stagnant water, the spread of disease, and degradation of living conditions, particularly during the monsoon season.

Therefore, the case of Manghopir exemplifies how a historically significant urban space home to religious heritage, ethnic diversity, and economic activity can become environmentally degraded and socio-spatially fragmented in the absence of proactive planning and governance.

5. Conclusion

This study of Manghopir, Karachi, divulges the multifaceted and layered urban dynamics of a historically significant yet critically underserved neighbourhood. The total area of 965 acres was divided into four distinct zones, showcasing religious-cultural, industrial, mixed-density residential, and high-density residential microcosms, based on which the research identifies issues related to urban informality, infrastructural decay, and environmental neglect within the broader context of Karachi's peripheral growth. Across all zones, a recurring pattern of worsening road conditions, uneven utility distribution, unfettered industrial expansion, and lack of green infrastructure occurs.

The issues are most prominent due to the poor facilitation, availability of political influence, the least concern of responsible authorities, and a lack of awareness and proper education of the locals.

Squatter settlements with the legalization of fewer houses have become a barrier in addressing the issues to the government authorities concerned, which might need to put extra bits of effort into improving

the living conditions of the area. Certain non-profitable organizations and NGOs with the members of civil society have been working tirelessly to improve the conditions of different scales based on the funds and their capabilities. The commercial hub in this area has been noted to increase significantly with the increase in the residential plots and population of the area. The increased population rises the demands of the area and asks for more facilities with better infrastructure but the unsolved problems are also increasing and becoming worse by the passage of time. The study provides all the aspects of built and physical environment and the area's potential to improve the conditions just by providing bits of solutions that may bring major changes on the positive side and may help in providing people with better living conditions.

The findings of this research highlight the importance of adopting an inclusive, participatory, and spatially contextualized urban strategy to address Manghopir's challenges. Interventions can focus on constructing planned roads and by using a layers of crushed sandstone, crush and asphalt material. Appropriate construction technique and timely maintenance will help the traffic flow to move rapidly it will also reduce the air pollution and save a sewerage system which is located below ground level. A parallel parking along the services lane of about 12 feet should be provided for the local vendors to avoid blockage of vehicular flow. Installing crossover metal designed pedestrian bridge will help people to cross the road easily within the heavy vehicular flow. This is a safe and comfortable circulation for pedestrian movement. Provision of a 5'-0" x 15'-0" bus stand with separated seating space for both male and female can be designed using marble as a local material that represents an identity of entire Manghopir area and the design of bus stop will help providing cool waiting spot as well as will be used as a marketing spot for local vendors. A dedicated 4ft wide red-patched lane for cyclists to have easy and risk-free movement along the road. Provision of 6ft 6-foot-wide median as a green belt helps reduce noise and air pollution by using a combination of neem and kekar trees because they have a large foliage of 20 feet to 30 feet, alongside roads and footpaths. A lily plant (Green strip Leaves) and zohra (Red Flowers) are proposed to make an aesthetically pleasing environment in Manghopir Road. Moreover, a directional signage board can be

proposed on roads after every 1 km and at corners of main streets, which represents a street name, numbers, and blocks.

Ultimately, Manghopir represents not just a local case but a wider urban condition affecting rapidly expanding cities in the Global South, demonstrating the possibilities of low-cost interventions, and the potential of integrated planning to transform marginalized spaces into functional, inclusive urban environments. The findings from Manghopir offer broader insights for sustainable development in other rapidly urbanizing peri-urban settlements in the Global South. This research advocates for a shift from reactive and fragmented urban management to proactive, inclusive, and localized planning strategies ones that recognize the socio-spatial diversity of marginalized areas and work towards equitable urban futures.

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